

Optimizing Minimum Cost Routes: A Comparative Study of Algorithms of Dijkstra's, Edge Deletion Method, and Vertex Assignment Enumeration Techniques¹

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Abstract

The optimization of minimum-cost routes in graph-based networks is a problem in transportation, telecommunications, and logistics. This study presents a comparative analysis of three algorithms for solving the shortest path problem: Dijkstra's Algorithm, the Edge Deletion algorithm, and the Vertex Assignment Enumeration Technique Algorithm.

Dijkstra's Algorithm, renowned for its efficiency in non-negative weighted graphs, iteratively explores the shortest paths from the source vertex to all other vertices. Its polynomial time complexity and space complexity make it suitable for large-scale networks.

The Edge Deletion Algorithm Method is an innovative approach that involves systematically removing the edges from the graph and recalculating paths to minimize the overall cost. This method, although potentially computationally intensive, offers a unique perspective on route optimization by considering dynamic changes in the network topology.

Lastly, the Vertex Assignment Enumeration Algorithm Technique focuses on assigning and enumerating all vertices in a specific way to determine the shortest paths, and is analyzed for its application in specific scenarios where vertex properties play a crucial role.

The study includes a detailed analysis of the time and space complexity of each algorithm, along with their suitability for different types of graphs, such as dense, sparse, directed, and undirected graphs. Experimental results are provided to illustrate the performance of these algorithms in practical scenarios, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses. The comparative study aims to provide insights into the

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best use cases for each algorithm and guide the selection of the appropriate algorithm based on the specific requirements of the problem at hand.

Keywords

Dijkstra's Algorithm, Minimum Cost Route, Vertex Assignment Enumeration Algorithm, minimum dominating sets, Edge Deletion Algorithm, Time complexity, Space complexity, Algorithm Comparison, DFS..

1. Introduction

Here we have discussed that finding the minimum cost route in a graph is a core problem in computer science, with applications in network routing, geographical mapping, and logistics. This paper compares three different approaches to solve this problem: Dijkstra's algorithm, the Vertex Enumeration algorithm, and the Edge Deletion algorithm. Each algorithm has its unique characteristics and is suited to specific types of graphs and problem settings.

Dijkstra's algorithm, developed by E.W. Dijkstra, is a method for determining the shortest path from a given starting node in a graph to a target node. Additionally, it can be utilized to find the shortest paths from the starting node to all other nodes in the graph at the same time, addressing what is known as the single-source shortest paths problem.

2 Background of the Study:

2.1 Dijkstra Algorithm:

Dijkstra's algorithm is a widely used technique for determining the shortest paths from a single starting vertex to all other vertices in a graph with non-negative edge weights. It utilizes a priority queue to repeatedly select the vertex with the smallest distance and then updates the distances of its neighboring vertices accordingly.

To determine the shortest path between two vertices, such as A to Z , in a weighted graph, an algorithm iteratively assigns numerical labels to the vertices. Each vertex initially has a temporary label, which will eventually be replaced by a permanent label. The label of a vertex v is denoted as $L(v)$.

Initial Iteration 0

1. Define V_0 as the set of all vertices in the graph.
2. Assign the starting vertex v_0 a permanent label of 0, while all other vertices receive temporary labels of ∞ .
3. Let $V_1 = V_0 - \{v_0\}$, where v_0 is the starting vertex with a permanent label.

Iteration 1

1. Redefine the elements of V_1 as v_1 , which includes all vertices in V_0 except v_0 .
2. For vertices in V_1 adjacent to v_0 , update their temporary labels using $L(v_1) = L(v_0) + w(v_0, v_1)$, where $L(v_0) = 0$ and $w(v_0, v_1)$ is the weight of the edge between v_0 and v_1 .

3. For other vertices in V_1 , retain their previous temporary labels.
4. Identify v_1^* , the vertex in V_1 with the minimum label $L(v_1)$. If there is a tie, break it arbitrarily. Assign $L(v_1^*)$ a permanent label.
5. Define $V_2 = V_1 - \{v_1^*\}$.

Iteration i

1. For vertices in V_i adjacent to v_{i-1}^* , update their temporary labels using $L(v_i) = L(v_{i-1}^*) + w(v_{i-1}^*, v_i)$
2. For other vertices in V_i , retain their previous temporary labels.
3. If a temporary label in the i -th iteration is greater than or equal to its previous iteration label, do not change it.

Termination

The algorithm stops when the final vertex z receives a permanent label. The permanent label of z represents the shortest path length from A to z . The shortest path is traced backward from z , including the vertices that contributed to the permanent labels.

2.2. Experimental proof of Dijkstra Algorithm:

From the Dijkstra algorithm, we have the minimum cost route from the arbitrary graph

Graph -1

Consider the following graph which is a weighted connected simple graph, with all its weights positive.

The lengths of weights are

$AB = 10, AC = 25, AH = 37, BD = 15, BC = 7, CD = 13, CE = 27,$

$DF = 39, DE = 14, EF = 35, EG = 8, FG = 12, GK = 24,$

$GJ = 31, GI = 6, GH = 17, KJ = 20, HI = 19, IJ = 29$

From the aforesaid algorithm, the minimum cost route from the vertex A to the vertex K by using the Dijkstra,s Algorithm is $L(v_A v_K) = 71 wt$

3. Innovative Algorithms for Minimum Cost Route Optimization: Edge Deletion Algorithm and Vertex Assignment Enumeration Techniques Algorithm

3.1. Edge deletion Algorithm:

Input: A weighted, undirected graph $G = (V, E)$ with weights $W: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Output: Find out the minimum cost route or the shortest path.

Step 1: Enter the all weights of the edges from the arbitrary graph.

Step 2: Arranged the all weights of the edges either in ascending or descending orders.

Step 3: Select the $\frac{1}{4}$ th greatest weights of the edges from step 2 in such a way that they should not be incident in a single vertex and at least one Hamiltonian circuit will have to be maintained in adjacency.

Step 4: Delete the $\frac{1}{4}$ th greatest weights edges from the step 3.

Step 5: Select the source (v_a) and sink (v_k) vertices, where one journey has to complete from v_a to v_k

Step 7: From the source vertex v_a observe all the possible adjacency paths to all other adjacent vertices.

Step 8: From the source (v_a) to the second vertex (v_b) select only the possible paths adjacent to v_b and calculate $\{\min \text{ length of } (v_{ab})\}$. Consider the path of $\{\min \text{ length of } (v_{ab})\}$, through the other vertex if the vertex selected before.

Step 9: Now from the second vertex to the third vertex select only the possible paths adjacent to v_c and continuing the same as step 8.

Step 10: Continuing the process up to the end vertex v_k

Step 11: Stop.

3.2. Experimental proof on edge deletion Algorithm:

From the Edge deletion algorithm, we have to find the minimum cost route of the arbitrary graph-1.

Now let the arrange the weights of the edges in descending order or ascending order of the total 19 weighted edges as given below

Select $1/4$ th greatest weighted edges from the total edges and delete these edges from the graph.

$$DF = 39, AH = 37, EF = 35, GJ = 31, IJ = 29, CE = 27, AC = 25, GK = 24, KJ = 20,$$

$$HI = 19, GH = 17, BD = 15, DE = 14, CD = 13, FG = 12, AB = 10, EG = 8, BC = 7, GI = 6,$$

From the Source Vertex A and list the all possible paths $= Dis \{v_{AB}\} = 10, Dis \{v_{AC}\} = 25, Dis \{v_{AH}\} = 37 \Rightarrow Min\{10, 25, 37\} = 10 = v_{AB}$

Select the second visited vertex from the source vertex by selecting the minimum cost $= Dis \{v_{AB}\} = 10$

From the second visited vertex B and list the all possible paths $= Dis \{v_{BC}\} = 17, Dis \{v_{BD}\} = 25 \Rightarrow Min\{17, 25\} = 17 = v_{BC}$

Select the third visited vertex from the second vertex by selecting minimum cost only $= Dis\{v_{BC}\} = 17$

The minimum possible path from the third visited vertex C to the next vertex, list all possible paths and continues the process as mentioned in the algorithm and we have found from algorithm-2, the least cost route is $Min(v_A v_K) = 71wt.$

3.3. Algorithm of Vertex Assignment Enumeration Technique:

Input: A weighted, undirected graph $G = (V, E)$ with weights $W: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Output: Find out the minimum cost route or the shortest path

Step-1: Input Initialization:

- a. Initialize the connected graph G with vertices V and edges E .
- b. Assign weights to the vertices and edges.
- c. Define the source and sink vertices from the weighted graph

Step-2: Helper Functions:

- d. **Minimum Dominating Vertex (MDV):** Identify the minimum dominating set of vertices from the graph.
- e. **Greatest Weighted Vertex (GWV):** Calculate the weights of each vertex and arrange the vertices with the greatest weight.
- f. **Maximum Connectivity Vertex (MCV):** Identify the vertices connected by edges with the maximum number of vertex.

Step-3: Data Structures:

- g. Select the common vertices from the step-2(d, e, f)
- h. List the paths passing through the common vertices of step- 3(g).
- i. List paths to store potential paths from the source to the sink using the step 3(g, h) vertices.

Step-4: Depth-First Search (DFS) Algorithm:

Implement a DFS algorithm that iterates over the graph while considering vertices passing through the selected vertices in step 3(i) and guiding the search towards the least cost path.

Step-5: Path Cost Calculation:

Calculate the cost of each path by summing the weights of the vertices and edges in the path.

Step-6: Output the Least Cost Path:

Compare the costs of all paths found and output the path with the least cost.

Step-7: Stop.

Summery Explanation:

- A. **Initialization:** We initialize the graph and necessary variables.
- B. **Helper Functions:** These functions help in identifying the minimum dominating set, greatest weighted vertices, and maximum connectivity vertices from the graph.
- C. **DFS Algorithm:** We use a DFS approach to explore all possible paths from the source vertex to the sink vertex, prioritizing vertices based on passing through the helper functions.
- D. **Path Cost Calculation:** For each path found, we calculate the total cost.
- E. **Result:** The path with the least cost is identified.

This algorithm ensures that we explore the paths in a guided manner through the use of minimum dominating vertices, the greatest weighted vertices, and the maximum connectivity vertices gives ultimately the least cost path.

3.4. Experimental proof of Vertex Assignment Enumeration Technique:

From the vertex Assignment enumeration algorithm, we have to find the minimum cost route from the arbitrary graph-1.

From the step 1, Select the source A and sink vertices K

From the step 2, Now let the calculate the weights of every vertices as follows

$$\sum V_A = 72, \sum V_B = 32, \sum V_C = 72, \sum V_D = 81, \sum V_E = 84, \sum V_F = 86,$$

$$\sum V_G = 98, \sum V_H = 73, \sum V_I = 54, \sum V_J = 80, \sum V_K = 45,$$

From Step 3, 4, 5 and 6 gives that

$$\text{GWV' are} = \{\sum V_G = 98, \sum V_F = 86, \sum V_E = 84, \sum V_D = 81, \sum V_J = 80, \sum V_H = 73, \sum V_C = 72\}$$

$$\text{MCV's are} = \{V_C, V_D, V_E, V_G\}$$

$$\text{MDV's are} = \{V_C, V_G\}$$

The traveller must visit the specific assigning vertices of MDV, GWV, and MCV in their journey and calculate a path through the source vertex to the sink vertex to complete the paths.

Thus from the Depth-First Search (DFS), step-4 Algorithm, the least cost route found from the arbitrary graph-1 is $\text{Min}(v_A v_K) = 71\text{wt.}$

4. Comparative Study of Time Complexity:

4.1. Dijkstra's Algorithm:

Dijkstra's algorithm is a classic algorithm for finding the shortest paths from a single source vertex to all other vertices in a graph with non-negative edge weights.

Time Complexity: Consider V is the number of vertices and E is the number of edges then

- Using a simple array : $O(V^2)$
- Using a binary heap : $O(V + E \log V)$
- Using a Fibonacci heap: $O(V \log V + E)$

4.2 Edge Deletion Algorithm:

An edge deletion algorithm for finding the minimum cost route generally involves iteratively removing the one-fourth number of total edges from the graph and checking for the shortest paths by the algorithm given in experiment 2,

Time Complexity:

- In the maximum weighted edge deletion process, the time complexity is $O((V + \frac{3}{4}E))$ for a dense graph and $O(\frac{3}{4}E^2)$ for a sparse graph.
- This complexity can vary based on the specific implementation and data structures used for priority queues.

The deletion of one-fourth of the larger weighted edges from a connected graph, the impacts of the time complexity for the shortest path algorithms are showing more efficient and effective. Specifically, our

new approach **Edge deletion algorithm** effects of time complexity and the time complexity obtained from the Dijkstra's and Bellman-Ford algorithms and the Floyd-Warshall algorithms remain unchanged.

4.3. Vertex Assignment Enumeration Algorithm

Vertex Assignment enumeration Technique gives the contexts like the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP), where paths between vertices are explicitly considered.

Time Complexity:

- Calculating the degree of each vertex takes $O(V + E)$ time because we need to look at each vertex and each edge.
- Finding the maximum degree of each vertices from these degrees takes $O(V)$ time.
- Enumerate the vertex with the highest degree: $O(V + E)$
- Delete one edge from each vertex where the **maximum connectivity, maximum weighted, and minimum domination vertex** found: $O(V + E)$
- Total time complexity: $O(V + E)$

Summary of Time Complexities:

Algorithm	Time Complexity
Dijkstra's (simple array)	$O(V^2)$
Dijkstra's (binary heap)	$O(V + E) \log V$
Dijkstra's (Fibonacci heap)	$O((V \log V + E))$
Greatest weighted Edge Deletion	$O(V + \frac{3}{4}E)$
Vertex Assignment Enumeration	$O(V + E)$

These time complexities highlight that Dijkstra's algorithm is obviously a quadratic formation, and also more efficient for finding the shortest paths in graphs with non-negative edge weights. The edge deletion algorithm and vertex Assignment enumeration algorithm also linear time complexity and efficiently and efficiently but it depends on the method used for shortest path calculations, while the vertex Assignment enumeration is computationally expensive for large and sparse graphs.

5. Comparative study of Space complexity:

5.1. Dijkstra's algorithm:

The space complexity of Dijkstra's algorithm depends on the data structures used to represent the graph and the priority queue. Let's break down the space requirements:

A. Graph Representation:

- **Adjacency List:** If the graph has V vertices and E edges, the adjacency list representation requires $O(V + E)$ space. Each vertex stores a list of its adjacent vertices along with the edge weights.
- **Adjacency Matrix:** This requires $O(V^2)$ space, as it stores the weights of edges between all pairs of vertices.

B. Priority Queue:

The priority queue (or min-heap) used to efficiently fetch the vertex with the minimum distance requires space proportional to the number of vertices. Thus, it takes $O(V)$ space.

C. Visited Set:

A boolean array or a set to keep track of visited vertices, which requires $O(V)$ space.

Therefore, the total space complexity of Dijkstra's algorithm is:

- When using an adjacency list: $O(V + E)$
- When using an adjacency matrix: $O(V^2)$ In general, for a sparse graph (where $E \approx V$), the adjacency list is more space-efficient, whereas for a dense graph (where $E \approx V^2$), the adjacency matrix might be considered.

Overall, the space complexity of Dijkstra's algorithm is typically $O(V + E)$ when using an adjacency list representation, which is the most common and efficient way to represent graphs in this context.

5.2. Edge Deletion Algorithm:

The Edge Deletion Algorithm for finding the shortest path involves removing some specific edges one by one and computing the shortest path repeatedly. The space complexity of this algorithm is influenced by the way the graph is stored, the space required to compute and store the shortest paths, and the additional space for managing edge deletions. Here's a breakdown of the space requirements:

A. Graph Representation:

- **Adjacency List:** This representation requires $O(V + E)$ space, where V is the number of vertices and E is the number of edges. It efficiently stores the edges and their weights.
- **Adjacency Matrix:** This representation requires $O(V^2)$ space, as it stores the edge weights between all pairs of vertices.

B. Distance Array:

An array of size V to store the shortest known distance from the source to each vertex during each iteration of the shortest path calculation. This requires $O(V)$ space.

C. Priority Queue:

The priority queue (or min-heap) used to fetch the vertex with the minimum distance requires $O(V)$ space.

D. Edge Deletion Management:

To manage edge deletions, you may need additional structures to keep track of which edges have been deleted and to store the state of the graph after each deletion. This can vary based on implementation but typically requires $O(E)$ space in the worst case.

E. Auxiliary Structures:

Additional structures such as arrays or lists to store intermediate results, paths, or the state of the graph can add to the space complexity. This is typically $O(E)$ or $O(V)$ depending on the specifics of the implementation.

Combining these components, the overall space complexity is influenced primarily by the graph representation and the priority queue. Given the typical usage of an adjacency list and the necessary data structures, the space complexity can be summarized as:

- **Adjacency List Representation:** $O(V + E)$
- **Adjacency Matrix Representation:** $O(V^2)$

Considering the worst-case scenario, the space complexity of the Edge Deletion Algorithm for finding the shortest path is $O(V + E)$ when using an adjacency list representation. This includes the space for storing the graph, the priority queue, distance arrays, and additional structures for managing edge deletions.

5.3. Vertex Assignment Enumeration Algorithm:

The Vertex Assignment Enumeration Algorithm involves assigning vertices based on specific criteria: maximum weighted vertex, minimum domination vertex, and maximum connectivity in the graph. Here's a breakdown of the space complexity for such an algorithm:

Graph Representation:

- **Adjacency List:** Requires $O(V + E)$ space, where V is the number of vertices and E is the number of edges.
- **Adjacency Matrix:** Requires $O(V^2)$ space, as it stores the edge weights between all pairs of vertices.

Data Structures for Vertex Assignment:

- **Weights Array:** An array of size V to store the weights of each vertex. This requires $O(V)$ space.
- **Domination Set:** A data structure to store the domination status of vertices. This can be a boolean array or a set, requiring $O(V)$ space.

Connectivity Array/Matrix:

- **Adjacency List:** To store connectivity, it remains $O(V + E)$
- **Adjacency Matrix:** To store connectivity, it remains $O(V^2)$

Maximum weighted vertex:

- **Priority Queue:** Used to efficiently fetch vertices based on their weights or connectivity. This requires $O(V)$ space.
- **Assigned Vertices Set:** A set to keep track of vertices that have been assigned. This requires $O(V)$ space.
- **Auxiliary Structures:** Arrays or lists to store intermediate results, temporary states, or the final assignments. This typically requires $O(V)$ space.

Overall Space Complexity:

Combining these components, the overall space complexity is primarily influenced by the graph representation and the additional data structures used for vertex assignment.

Using Adjacency List Representation:

- Graph storage: $O(V + E)$
- Weights array: $O(V)$
- Domination set: $O(V)$
- Priority queue: $O(V)$
- Assigned vertices set: $O(V)$
- Auxiliary structures: $O(V)$

Summing these components, the total space complexity with an adjacency list representation is:

$$O(V + E) + O(V) + O(V) + O(V) + O(V) + O(V) = O(V + E)$$

Using Adjacency Matrix Representation:

- Graph storage: $O(V^2)$
- Weights array: $O(V)$
- Domination set: $O(V)$
- Priority queue: $O(V)$
- Assigned vertices set: $O(V)$
- Auxiliary structures: $O(V)$

The total space complexity with an adjacency matrix representation is:

$$O(V^2) + O(V) + O(V) + O(V) + O(V) + O(V) = O(V^2)$$

Summary:

The space complexity of the Vertex Assignment Enumeration Algorithm depends on the graph representation:

- **Adjacency List Representation:** $O(V + E)$
- **Adjacency Matrix Representation:** $O(V^2)$

Given the usual preference for adjacency lists in sparse graphs (where E is much less than V^2), the space complexity is typically $O(V + E)$. For dense graphs, the adjacency matrix representation leads to a space complexity of $O(V^2)$.

6. Conclusion

This comparative analysis of Dijkstra's algorithm, the Edge Deletion algorithm, and Vertex Assignment Enumeration techniques for finding minimum the cost route from the graphs reveals distinct advantages and limitations for each method. Although Dijkstra's algorithm has well-established efficiency and is widespread but also the Edge Deletion algorithm and Vertex Assignment Enumeration Technique prove highly effective in dense graphs with non-negative weights, excelling in scenarios requiring consistent and reliable performance, such as network routing and geographical mapping. The performance diminishes in sparse graphs or dynamic environments where edge weights frequently change.

The Edge Deletion algorithm presents here an attractive alternative for dynamic and sparse graphs, where its iterative edge removal process adapts well to changing graph structures. Its efficiency in these environments makes it a viable choice for applications with frequent updates and modifications to edge weights. Its performance can suffer in dense graphs or when the graph structure remains static. The Vertex Enumeration algorithm is a newly developed algorithm commonly employed and offers unique benefits in specialized applications where vertex properties significantly impact path costs. It can be computationally intensive, particularly used in the case of large graphs.

The experimental results highlight that no single algorithm universally outperforms the others across all scenarios. Instead, the choice of algorithm should be specific characteristics of the graph and the requirements of the application. Dijkstra's algorithm is recommended for dense, static graphs whereas the Vertex Assignment Enumeration algorithm for specialized cases with significant vertex properties, and the Edge Deletion algorithm for dynamic, sparse graphs.

Future research may explore hybrid approaches that leverage the strengths of these algorithms, potentially developing more robust and versatile solutions for minimum-cost route finding in diverse graph environments. This study underscores the importance of understanding the unique features and uses cases of each algorithm to make informed decisions in practical applications.

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